

A STUDY ON THE CORRELATION BETWEEN STUDY HABITS ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF B. ED DISTANCE LEARNERS

Yamini Salian

Seva Sadan's College of Education, Ulhasnagar – 421 003

Email: yamini.salian@yahoo.co.in

Paper Received On: 23 May 2023

Peer Reviewed On: 25 May 2023

Published On: 1 June 2023

Abstract

Education's role as a tool for social change determines a nation's overall growth. The 1964–1966 education commission referred to education as the "one vehicle of peaceful social development." From a policy perspective, the education challenge saw education as a catalyst to turn a stagnant society into one that is dedicated to growth and progress. As a result, the educational system may and must undergo radical change as part of the revolutionary restructuring of the current socioeconomic order." The same document notes that education's primary objective is to "build an energetic, thriving, and united nation that can provide its people with the resources they need to live better, more meaningful lives. According to Smith (1961), a student's capacity for learning is impacted by their learning strategies, goal-setting, time commitment, level of engagement with the subject matter, the scope of the learning environment, and the extent of application of what they have learned. Students who are intelligent and ambitious are more likely to develop effective study habits. A person with good study habits and intelligence can excel beyond the limitations imposed by intelligence, earning him the title of an overachiever. Unhealthy study habits create barriers in the way of a person's success and hinder them from fully utilising their strengths, which leads to them performing poorly in the academic field and becoming underachievers. Therefore, establishing productive study habits is essential to obtaining a satisfying degree of success. Evans and Smith [1970] emphasised the need of developing efficient "study habits" for a smooth transition to college. Successful college students have distinct study habits from unsuccessful ones. Recitation, using textbooks, participating in class, and setting aside time for study are all seen as acceptable study practises. The study habits questionnaire selected by the researcher for the present study was a standardized test prepared by M.N. Palsane and Anuradha Sharma. It was divided into eight areas. They are budgeting time, Physical conditions of Study, Reading ability, Note-taking, Factors in Learning Motivation, Memory, Taking Examinations, and Health. The present study was done to know the correlation between study habits and academic achievement of B.Ed distance learners. The sample size for the present study was comprised of 300 B.Ed distance learners from YCMOU and IGNOU. The Tools used for collecting the data were the Study habits questionnaire and the Academic Achievement Results of the Students. Data were analysed by using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation. A significant correlation between study habits and academic achievement was found. There was found to be a significant relationship between the study habits of more than 40 years of age of B.Ed distance learners and academic achievement. Also, there is a relationship between the study habits of male B.Ed distance learners and academic achievement. It was also found that there was no effect of study habits on Academic Achievement of B.Ed distance learners with regards to the

type of school which they are teaching. *Conceptual definition*-Crow & Crow (1992) claim that having a plan or place to study, a set schedule, and taking concise, well-organized notes are all helpful study habits. A student must select the knowledge that is crucial to their studies and then make an opinion on that information. *Operational definition*- This study focuses on how students organise their private readings after learning in the classroom and how they are directly influenced by other external factors. The key aspects of a person's study habits are note-taking, learning motivation, memory reading practises, learning strategies, memory, time management, study conditions, physical health, exams, and evaluations.

Keywords: Study habits, Academic achievement, B.Ed distance learners

Scholarly Research Journal's is licensed Based on a work at www.srjis.com

Introduction

Academic success is a performance indicator that demonstrates how well an individual succeeded regarding certain goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, and university. The majority of educational systems' cognitive objectives either include the acquisition of knowledge and comprehension in a specific intellectual discipline or are generic (like critical thinking) (e.g., numeracy, literacy, science, history). Therefore, it is important to think of academic achievement as a complicated idea that encompasses many different learning domains. The topic of academic achievement is fairly broad and involves a wide range of educational outcomes, therefore the definition of academic performance depends on the measures used to define it. Given the significance of academic accomplishment for both individuals and society as a whole, it is not unexpected that many scientists, including those in the fields of psychology and education, have focused their research on this topic.

Need and Significance of the Study

Study habits are the key to any student's academic achievement. Researchers worldwide have given serious and significant attention to learning styles, thinking patterns, and study habits. The research has unequivocally shown that study habits and learning preferences have a significant impact on the students in the classroom and the educational outcomes. They have an impact on how teachers convey information, engage with students, organise classroom activities, oversee coursework, and integrate students into society. The researcher desires to know the correlation between study habits and academic achievement. The researcher has conducted a present study to know the relationship between study habits and academic achievement of B Ed distance learners.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the study habits of B Ed distance learners

2. To study the relationship between study habits and academic achievement of B Ed distance learners.
3. To study the relationship between study habits and academic achievement in B Ed distance learners with regards to i) age ii) gender iii) medium of instruction

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is no significant relationship between study habits and academic achievement of B Ed distance learners.
2. There is no significant relationship between study habits and academic achievement of B Ed distance learners; i) age ii) gender iii) medium of instruction

Delimitation of the study

1. This study is limited to B Ed students of IGNOU and YCMOU.
2. This study is limited to B Ed students of English and Marathi mediums.
3. This study is limited to IGNOU and YCMOU B Ed study centres of the Mumbai region.

Methodology used for the study

The investigator selected quantitative research for the present study. The study is based on the effect of the study habits of B. Ed distance learners on academic achievement. The investigator used the Purposive and Convenient Sampling method and selected 300 distance learners from IGNOU and YCMOU learning centres.

Sample of the study

The researcher selected 300 B.Ed distance learners randomly from English and Marathi as the final sample size for the present study.

Tools used for the study

The researcher used the following tools for the present study;

The study habits questionnaire selected by the researcher for the present study was a standardized test prepared by M.N. Palsane and Anuradha Sharma.

The study habits questionnaire comprised 45 items covering certain areas of study habits. It was divided into eight areas. They are budgeting time, Physical conditions of Study, Reading ability, Note-taking, Factors in Learning Motivation, Memory, Taking Examinations, and Health

The study habit questionnaire was prepared in English and Marathi language. The reliability of study habit questionnaire is 0.88. There was an area-wise distribution of items. Three choices

always or Mostly, Sometimes and Never were given for answering each item. The students were asked to give a response by putting a tick mark against the selected choice. The result in the form of a percentage was used to know the academic achievement of the selected B.Ed distance learners for the present study.

Statistical Analysis

(1) Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Technique was used by the investigator to study the correlation between study habits and academic achievement of B. Ed distance learners as per Gender, age, type of school and medium of instruction separately.

Table 1 shows Learning style and Academic Achievement mean score and standard deviation as per background variables.

Correlation	Variable	N	Pearson’s Co-efficient Correlation Calculated r value	Pearson’s Co-efficient Correlation Tabulated r value	Result
Study Habits and Academic Achievement	Study habits	300	0.120	0.1128	Significant at 0.05 level
	Male	169	0.156	0.1475	Significant at 0.05 level
	Female	131	0.067	0.1592	Not significant
	More than 40 years	69	0.379	0.3017	Significant at 0.01 level
	Less than 40 years	231	0.037	0.236 0.1619	Not significant

Findings

The findings obtained from the present research were;

1. A significant correlation between the study habits of B Ed distance learners and their academic achievement was obtained.
2. A significant correlation between the study habits of male B Ed distance learners and their academic achievement was obtained.
3. A significant correlation between the study habits of B Ed distance learners of more than 40 years of age and their academic achievement was obtained.

Conclusion

There seems to be a positive correlation between the study habits of B Ed distance learners and academic achievement was obtained. Good study habits, such as organization, time management, and active engagement with the material, enhance the effectiveness of learning. When students develop effective study strategies, they can optimize their study time and absorb information more efficiently, leading to improved academic performance. It was seen that there exists a positive correlation between study habits and academic achievement in male B Ed distance learners. This means that students who have better study habits, such as time management skills, good note-taking skills, and effective study strategies, tend to perform better academically compared to those who do not have such habits. Also, males get more time compared to females due to which they have better study habits. There is a significant difference in study habits of more than 40 years of age of B.Ed. distance learners and academic achievement. Adult learners who are over 40 years old tend to have more motivation and dedication to their studies compared to younger students. They also have more life experience, which can help them understand the material better and apply it to their real-life situations. In addition, adult learners are more likely to have developed effective study habits over time, which can contribute to their academic success.

References

- Best, John W. and Kahn, J. V. (2007). *Research in Education*, New Delhi, Prentice Hall of India Private.
- Biswas, P.K. (1999) *Freshers in IGNOU: A study of their awareness, interest and motivation*, *Indian Journal of open learning* 8(3) 273-282
- Crow, R.D. and A. Crow,
- R Sherafat, C Murthy. (2016). *A Study of Study Habits and Academic Achievement among Secondary and Senior Secondary School Students of Mysore City*. *International Journal of Indian Psychology* 3 (2), DOI: 10.25215/0302.055, DIP: 18.01.055/20160302
- Rabia, M, Mubarak, N, Tallat H, & Nasir W (2017). *A Study on Study Habits and Academic Performance of Students*. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 7(10), 891–897
- Koul Lokesh (1997) *Fifth Survey of Educational Research, Open and Distance Learning, Trend Reports: New Delhi, NCER*
- Sharma R.A (2008). *Distance education, Meerut: International publishing house*

Online References

- <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in:8443/>
- <https://materchristi.libguides.com/c.php?g=169439&p=1114508>
- <https://www.dovepress.com/relationship-between-study-habits-and-academic-achievement-in-students-peer-reviewed-fulltext-article-AMEP>